

Journal of Pure and Applied
Ultrasonics

Website : www.ultrasonicsindia.org

A Publication of Ultrasonics Society of India

Ultrasonic attenuation in yttrium monochalcogenides

Bhawan Jyoti^{1,*}, Devraj Singh², Shivani Kaushik³, Vyoma Balla⁴, Shikha Wadhwa⁵ and D.K. Pandey⁶

¹USICT, Guru Gobind Singh Indraprastha University, Sector16C, Dwarka, New Delhi-110078, India

²Amity Institute of Applied Sciences, Amity University, Noida-201313, India,

³State Council of Educational Research & Training Haryana, Gurugram-122 001, India

⁴Amity School of Engineering and Technology, Delhi, Noida-201313, India

⁵Amity Institute of Nanotechnology, Amity University, Noida-201313, India

⁶Department of Physics, P.P.N. (P.G.) College, Kanpur-208001, India

*E-mail: aabru_sharma@yahoo.co.in

The present paper reports ultrasonic properties of yttrium chalcogenides (YCh: Ch=S, Se and Te) along <110> direction in the temperature region 100-500 K. The Coulomb and Born-Mayer potential model is applied to compute the higher order elastic constants. These elastic constants are used to utilise for computing ultrasonic velocity, ultrasonic Grüneisen parameters, thermal conductivity and ultrasonic attenuation. Additionally, the second order elastic constants has been applied to evaluate many mechanical properties such as Young modulus, bulk modulus, Cauchy's relation, Zener's anisotropy factor, toughness to fracture ratio for the prediction about the chosen materials. The YCh follow the Born stability criterion, so these materials are mechanical stable. The toughness to fracture is greater than 0.57, so these materials are brittle in nature. The thermal conductivity is also computed by means of Slack and Berman approach. Finally the temperature ultrasonic attenuation due to phonon-phonon interaction and thermo-elastic relaxation mechanisms has been computed along <110> at room temperature. The achieved results for yttrium monochalcogenides are discussed with similar type of materials.

Keywords: Monochalcogenides, elastic constants, ultrasonic properties, thermal properties.

Introduction

The rare-earth compounds have been attracted for studies on their thermodynamic and lattice dynamical properties due to their unusual behaviour of phonon models in last years¹⁻⁵. The partially filled f-orbital leads to their unusual behaviour. The physical and mechanical properties of rare earth materials can be studied using ultrasonic methods⁶⁻⁷.

There are number of theoretical and experimental studies to analyse the unusual behaviour of yttrium mononictides and monochalcogenides. Vaitheeswaran *et al.*¹ deliberated the structural phase transition of yttrium monochalcogenides under high pressure. Shinde *et al.*² studied structural and phonon properties for yttrium monochalcogenides in rock salt structure using density field theory (DFT). Seddik *et al.*⁵ investigated yttrium chalcogenides for their structural, elastic and high pressure properties using full potential-linear

augmented plane wave (FP-LAPW) plus local orbital method using generalized gradient approximation (GGA). Roedhamer *et al.*⁸ used inelastic neutron scattering for measuring phonon dispersion of yttrium mono-sulphide. Hulliger and Hull⁹ observed super-conductivity in YCh (Ch=S, Se and Te). Tutüncü and Srivastava¹⁰ studied phonon anomalies and superconductivity in rock-salt YS using first principle method by applying plane wave pseudo potential method and DFT. The superconducting behaviour of YS and its phonon spectra were studied by Steiner *et al.*¹¹ which confirmed strong anomalies in the longitudinal- acoustic branch.

The authors did not find any evidence on ultrasonic properties of YCh. There is also no evidence for the thermo-physical study on yttrium monochalcogenides using ultrasonic wave. This motivates us to investigate ultrasonic properties of yttrium monochalcogenides in the temperature range 100-500 K.

The Coulomb and Born-Mayer potential has been applied to evaluate the second and third elastic order constants (SOECs and TOECs) in the temperature region 0-500K for the yttrium monochalcogenides. The SOECs have been utilized to calculate Young's modulus, shear modulus, bulk modulus, Poisson's ratio and Zener anisotropy at room temperature. Further ultrasonic wave velocity and Breazeale's non-linear parameter have been computed along $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction. The thermal conductivity is calculated using Slack and Berman approach¹². Finally, the ultrasonic attenuation due to phonon-phonon interaction and thermo-elastic mechanisms has been analysed using Mason's approach.

Theory

The SOECs and TOECs of YCh were computed using Coulomb and Born-Mayer potentials¹³ at absolute zero. The inter-ionic potential is the sum of Coulomb/electrostatic and Born-Mayer potential/repulsive potential:

$$\phi(r) = \phi(C) + \phi(B) \quad (1)$$

Where $\phi(C)$ is long range Coulomb/electrostatic potential and $\phi(B)$ is the short range Born-Mayer/repulsive potential, given as

$$\phi(C) = \pm(e^2 / r_0) \quad \text{and} \quad \phi(B) = A \exp(-r_0 / b). \quad (2)$$

Here A is the strength parameter, r_0 is the nearest neighbour distance, 'e' is electronic charge, b is the hardness parameter¹⁴.

$$A = -3b \frac{e^2}{r_0} S_3^{(1)} \frac{1}{6 \exp(-\rho_0) + 12\sqrt{2} \exp(-\sqrt{2}r_0)} \quad (3)$$

Leibfried and Hahn¹⁵ developed the lattice dynamical theory. As per this theory the lattice energy alters within temperature. Hence we add vibrational energy contribution to static component of an elastic constant. Then we get SOECs and TOECs at particular temperature

$$C_{IJ} = C_{IJ}^0 + C_{IJ}^{Vib} \quad \text{and} \quad C_{IJK} = C_{IJK}^0 + C_{IJK}^{Vib} \quad (4)$$

The elastic constants at higher temperature are calculated using the method developed by Mori and Hiki¹⁶. The detailed expressions to find out SOECs and TOECs have been given in our recent paper¹⁷.

The shear modulus (G), bulk modulus (B), Zener's anisotropy (A), Poisson's ratio (ν) and tetragonal moduli (C_S) for YCh are also evaluated using SOECs. The expressions for these mechanical constants are given in literature¹⁸.

The Breazeale's non linearity parameter for the distortion to ultrasonic wave propagation is the means of simple harmonic generation of longitudinal wave. Numerically it is negative ratio of non-linearity and linear term in nonlinear wave.

$$\beta = -\frac{3K_2 + K_3}{K_2} \quad (5)$$

K_2 and K_3 are linear combinations of SOECs and TOECs respectively¹⁹.

V_D is the Debye average velocity and is dependent on the longitudinal (V_L) and the shear (V_S) wave velocities with Eq. (6)²⁰:

$$V_D = \left[\frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{1}{V_L^3} + \frac{1}{V_{S1}^3} + \frac{1}{V_{S2}^3} \right) \right]^{-1/3} \quad (6)$$

V_L and V_S are computed with SOECs along $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction using Eq. (7)²¹.

$$\left. \begin{aligned} V_L &= \sqrt{\frac{C_{11} + C_{12} + 2C_{44}}{\rho}} \\ V_{S1} &= \sqrt{\frac{C_{44}}{\rho}} \quad \text{polarized along } \langle 001 \rangle \\ V_{S2} &= \sqrt{\frac{C_{11} - C_{12}}{\rho}} \quad \text{polarized along } \langle \bar{1}\bar{1}0 \rangle \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (7)$$

The thermal conductivity in the materials where there are no charge carriers is due to vibration of lattice ions. In the present work, Mourelli-Slack¹² approach is used to calculate thermal conductivity at a temperature near the Debye temperature of solids. The expression for thermal conductivity is given below:

$$\kappa = \frac{AM_a \theta_D \delta^3}{\gamma^2 T} \quad (8)$$

Where A is a constant having value 3.04×10^{-8} , M_a is the atomic mass (in amu), δ^3 is the volume per atom, γ represents the Grüneisen parameter.

There are several causes of ultrasonic attenuation *i.e.*, electron-phonon (e-p) interaction, phonon-phonon (p-p) interaction and thermo-elastic relaxation mechanisms. But at higher temperature e-p interaction is absent, because of no coupling between the electron and phonon. So p-p interaction and thermo-elastic loss play important role in high temperature regime.

The attenuation of ultrasonic waves may be due to thermo-elastic relaxation mechanism for longitudinal

waves can be evaluated by Mason expression^{22, 23}.

$$\left(\frac{\alpha}{f^2}\right)_{th} = \frac{4\pi^2 \langle \gamma_i^j \rangle^2 \kappa T}{2\rho V_L^3} \quad (9)$$

The Akhieser loss^{24, 25} (loss due to p-p interaction) is expressed as:

$$\left(\frac{\alpha}{f^2}\right)_{Akh.Long} = \frac{4\pi^2 \tau_{th} E_0 (D_L/3)}{2\rho V_L^3} \quad (10)$$

$$\left(\frac{\alpha}{f^2}\right)_{Akh.Long} = \frac{4\pi^2 \tau_{th} E_0 (D_L/3)}{2\rho V_L^3} \quad (11)$$

Where E_0 is the energy density and is a function of $\frac{\theta_D}{T}$.

τ^{th} is the thermal relaxation time and is given as:

$$\tau_{th} = \tau_s = \frac{\tau_{IL}}{2} = \frac{3\kappa}{C_V V_D^2} \quad (12)$$

D is the non-linearity parameter and is obtained using Eq. (13).

$$D = 9 \langle (\gamma_i^j)^2 \rangle - 3 \langle \gamma_i^j \rangle^2 \frac{C_V T}{E_0} \quad (13)$$

Where C_V is the specific heat capacity and is also function of $\frac{\theta_D}{T}$.

Results and Discussion

The SOECs and TOECs are calculated using Eqs. (1-4) using two basic parameters *i.e.* lattice parameter and hardness parameter. The lattice parameter^{1,2,5,6} for YS, YSe and YTe are 5.499Å, 5.736 Å and 6.13Å respectively. The hardness parameter¹⁴ is taken as 0.303 Å for all YCh. The calculated values of SOECs and TOECs for YCh (Ch: S, Se, Te) in the temperature range 0-500K are presented in Table 1.

It is seen that the magnitudes of C_{11} , C_{44} , C_{111} , C_{144} and C_{166} increase 19%, 2.4%, 6%, 3% and 2.3% respectively as we go from 0 K to 500 K. Whereas the magnitude of C_{12} , C_{112} and C_{123} decrease 25%, 23% and 69% respectively at temperature from 0 K to 500 K. The value of C_{456} remains constant. These variations are shown in Table 1. These values are pragmatic with monochalcogenides of lanthanum²³, neptunium²⁴ and europium²⁵. The greater value of elastic constants of YS among the yttrium monochalcogenides under study shows that it is stiffer and stable than the other compounds.

Cousin²⁶ and Hiki & Granato²⁷ proposed that Cauchy relation for SOECs and TOECs at 0K are:

$$C_{12}^0 = C_{44}^0; \quad C_{112}^0 = C_{166}^0; \quad C_{123}^0 = C_{144}^0 = C_{456}^0 \quad (14)$$

Table 1 – Temperature dependent SOECs and TOECs of yttrium monochalcogenides (in 10^{10}Nm^{-2}).

Material	Temp.(K)	C_{11}	C_{12}	C_{44}	C_{111}	C_{112}	C_{123}	C_{144}	C_{166}	C_{456}
YS	0	5.27	1.65	1.65	-86.45	-6.74	2.73	2.73	-6.74	2.73
	100	5.54	1.57	1.66	-88.20	-6.44	2.26	2.75	-6.79	2.73
	200	5.70	1.49	1.67	-88.83	-6.14	1.79	2.77	-6.81	2.73
	300	5.88	1.40	1.68	-89.68	-5.83	1.32	2.79	-6.84	2.73
	400	6.07	1.32	1.68	-90.60	-5.52	0.84	2.81	-6.87	2.73
	500	6.26	1.24	1.69	-91.54	-5.22	0.37	2.83	-6.90	2.73
YSe	0	4.86	1.37	1.37	-81.70	-5.58	2.31	2.31	-5.58	2.31
	100	5.09	1.29	1.38	-83.10	-5.27	1.83	2.33	-5.61	2.31
	200	5.26	1.21	1.38	-83.88	-4.97	1.35	2.34	-5.64	2.31
	300	5.44	1.13	1.39	-84.79	-4.65	0.87	2.36	-5.66	2.31
	400	5.62	1.05	1.39	-85.74	-4.34	0.38	2.38	-5.69	2.31
	500	5.81	0.97	1.40	-86.70	-4.03	-0.09	2.40	-5.71	2.31
YTe	0	4.25	1.02	1.02	-74.17	-4.13	1.77	1.77	-4.13	1.77
	100	4.45	0.95	1.03	-75.44	-3.82	1.28	1.78	-4.16	1.77
	200	4.61	0.87	1.03	-76.27	-3.51	0.78	1.80	-4.17	1.77
	300	4.78	0.80	1.04	-77.19	-3.19	0.29	1.81	-4.19	1.77
	400	4.96	0.72	1.04	-78.14	-2.88	-0.19	1.82	-4.21	1.77
	500	5.13	0.64	1.05	-79.10	-2.56	-0.69	1.84	-4.23	1.77

The Cauchy's relations are hold good at 0K as shown in Table 1. The deviation of SOECs and TOECs is found at higher temperatures, which provides information us that the forces become more ionic with increase in the temperature. This type of behaviour was existed in other rare-earth material^{6, 7, 20}.

The mechanical constants like tetragonal modulus (C_S), Zener anisotropy ratio (A), Young's modulus (Y), isotropic shear modulus (G), Poisson's ratio (ν) and B/G ratio at room temperature are obtained by using SOECs values at room temperature given in Table 2. The expressions used for their calculations are given in our previous paper²⁸.

The Born criterion²⁹ $C_S = (C_{11} - C_{12})/2 > 0$, $B_T = (C_{11} + 2C_{12})/3 > 0$ and $C_{44} > 0$ for stability is satisfied for all these materials. Hence these materials are mechanically stable. The ratio of isotropic shear modulus to bulk modulus *i.e.*, G/B (toughness/fracture) is greater than 0.57, so the materials have brittle nature. The nature of bonding forces can be analysed from Poisson's ratio. For central forces, the value of Poisson's ratio should lie in region $0.25 < \nu < 0.5$. For the material considered in our study the value does not fall in the range which means that the forces are non central³⁰. The value of Young's modulus is greater for YS and hence YS is stiffer than other materials. Figure 1 shows the values of B , C_S and G for both materials. B , C_S and G were found highest for YS. This indicates that YS is the most stable materials among them.

Table 2 – Mechanical constants for YCh (Ch: S, Se, Te).

Material	C_S^*	G^*	A	Y	ν	B/G
YS	2.24	1.88	0.775	4.64	0.23	0.65
YSe	2.15	1.65	0.64	4.09	0.23	0.65
YTe	1.99	1.35	0.52	3.34	0.23	0.64

*(in units 10^{10}Nm^{-2})

Table 3 – Temperature dependent ultrasonic velocities (10^3ms^{-1})

Temp. (K)	YS			YSe			YTe		
	V_L	$^aV_{SI}$	$^bV_{S2}$	V_L	$^aV_{SI}$	$^bV_{S2}$	V_L	$^aV_{SI}$	$^bV_{S2}$
100	3.28	1.85	2.86	2.78	1.52	2.53	2.44	1.28	2.36
200	3.3	1.85	2.95	2.79	1.53	2.61	2.46	1.28	2.44
300	3.32	1.86	3.04	2.81	1.53	2.7	2.47	1.29	2.52
400	3.33	1.86	3.13	2.83	1.53	2.78	2.49	1.29	2.6
500	3.35	1.87	3.22	2.85	1.54	2.86	2.51	1.29	2.68

^ashear waves polarized along $\langle 001 \rangle$ direction; ^bshear waves polarized along $\langle \bar{1}10 \rangle$ direction

Fig. 1. B , C_S and G at room temperature

The computed values of ultrasonic velocities are shown in Table 3. The values of Debye average velocity, Debye temperature and Breazeale's non-linearity parameter at room temperature are shown in Table 4.

The value for ultrasonic velocity for YS is greater in comparison to YSe and YTe so propagation of sound waves is better in YS. The Debye temperature decreases with increase in atomic number and lattice constant.

Table 4 – V_D , θ_D and β of YCh at 300K

Material	$\langle 110 \rangle$		
	V_D	θ_D	β
YS	2.39	258.75	5.89
YSe	1.99	206.54	5.91
YTe	1.71	166.07	5.94

This kind of behaviour is seen in holmium mononictides⁶. The non-linearity parameter (β) is a function of ratio of SOECs. This parameter is presented in Table 4. β is highest for YTe. So we can say here that β is directly proportional to molecular weight of the material.

Temperature dependent thermal conductivity for YCh is calculated using the Eq. (8) and is shown in Fig. 2. The value of thermal conductivity is inversely proportional to temperature as well as molecular weight of the given materials as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Variation of thermal conductivity with temperature along $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction

The temperature dependent thermo-elastic loss and Akhieser loss (due to p-p interaction for longitudinal and shear waves) are visualized in Figs. 3-6. It is observed from Figs. 3-6 that the thermal loss is mainly depends on the thermal conductivity. So it has more or less trend as observed for thermal conductivity. The Akhieser loss

Fig. 3. Thermal attenuation [in unit of $10^{-16} \text{Nps}^2 \text{m}^{-1}$] with temperature along $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction

Fig. 4. Ultrasonic attenuation $\alpha/f^2_{\text{Akh,shear.S1}}$ with temperature along $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction [in unit of $10^{-16} \text{Nps}^2 \text{m}^{-1}$]

Fig. 5. Ultrasonic attenuation [in unit of $10^{-16} \text{Nps}^2 \text{m}^{-1}$] with temperature along $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction

Fig. 6. Ultrasonic attenuation $\alpha/f^2_{\text{Akh,shear.S2}}$ with temperature along $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction [in unit of $10^{-16} \text{Nps}^2 \text{m}^{-1}$]

(loss due p-p interaction) increases with temperature along $\langle 110 \rangle$ direction. The loss due to p-p interaction has been affected by not only thermal conductivity but also many other factors such as energy density, density, acoustic coupling constants.

From Figs. 3-6, it is also noticeable that ultrasonic attenuation due to p-p interaction is predominant over thermo-elastic loss. This type of trend of ultrasonic loss is very similar to loss in case of monochalcogenides of lanthanum²³, lutetium³¹ and thulium³². The quantum of the thermal loss and Akhieser loss indicate that YCh have semiconducting behaviour.

Conclusions

We conclude following points on the basis of above discussion:

- The Coulomb and Born Mayer potential have been applied to calculate the higher order elastic constants successfully.
- The higher order elastic constants are higher for YS therefore mechanical properties of YS are better.
- According to Born criterion, these materials are stable as $B > 0$, $C_S > 0$ and $C_{44} > 0$.
- G/B values are greater than 0.57, so these materials are brittle in nature.
- The ultrasonic velocity is higher for YS among the chosen materials. So YS is better texture material.
- Breazeale's non-linearity parameter lies in the range from 0-16 which is typically the range of solids.
- The lowest attenuation is found in YS so the energy loss is lowest. Hence YS is most useful material for industrial purpose.

Hence these important discussed characteristics make yttrium monochalcogenides for possible under extreme condition. Such important feature would be very useful for improving the future performance of yttrium monochalcogenides and their futuristic applications.

References

- 1 **Vaitheeswaran G., Kanchana V., Svane A., Christensen N. E., Staun Olsen J., Jorgensen J.-E. and Gerward L.**, High-pressure structural study of yttrium monochalcogenides from experiment and theory, *Phys. Rev. B: Condens. Matter.* **83** (2011), 184108.
- 2 **Shinde S. M., Gupta S., Gupta S. K. and Jha P. R.**, Lattice dynamics and thermodynamical study of yttrium monochalcogenides, *Comput. Mat. Sc.* **92** (2014), 69-75.
- 3 **Sahoo B.D., Joshi K.D. and Gupta S.C.**, Pressure effect on elastic, lattice dynamic and superconducting behaviour of yttrium sulfide: A first principle study, *J. Appl. Phys.* **115** (2014), 123502.
- 4 **Maachou A., Aboura H., Amrani B., Khenata R., Bin-Omran S. and Varshney D.**, Structural stabilities, elastic and thermodynamic properties of scandium chalcogenides via first-principles calculations, *Comput. Mater. Sci.* **50** (2011), 3123-3130.
- 5 **Seddik T., Khenata R., Bouhemadou A., Guechi N., Sayede A., Varshney D., Al-Douri Y., Reshak A. H. and Bin-Omran S.**, External temperature and pressure effects on thermodynamic properties and mechanical stability of yttrium chalcogenides YX (X=S, Se and Te), *Physica B* **428** (2013), 78-88.
- 6 **Bhalla V., Singh D. and Jain S.K.**, Mechanical and thermophysical properties of rare-earth monpnictides, *Int. J. Comput. Mater. Sci. Eng.* **5** (2016), 1650012 (14pp).
- 7 **Bhalla V. and Singh D.**, Anisotropic assessment of ultrasonic wave velocity and thermal conductivity in ErX (X: n, As), *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.* **54** (2016), 40-45.
- 8 **Roedhammer P., Reichardt W. and Holtzberg F.**, Soft-mode behavior in the phonon dispersion of YS, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* **40** (1978), 465-468.
- 9 **Hulliger F. and Hull J.G.W.**, Superconductivity in rocksalt-type compounds, *Solid State Commun.* **8** (1970), 1379-1382.
- 10 **Tutüncü H.M. and Srivastava G.P.**, Ab-initio investigations of phonon anomalies and superconductivity in the rock-salt YS, *Philos. Mag.* **87** (2007) 4109-4118 .
- 11 **Steiner M.M., Eschrig H. and Monnier R.**, Longitudinal-acoustic-phonon softening in YS, LaS, and CeSe, *Phy. Rev. B* **45** (1992), 7183-7187.
- 12 **Morelli D.T. and Slack G.A.**, High Thermal Conductivity Materials, *Springer, New York*, (2006).
- 13 **Born M. and Mayer J.E.**, Zur Gittertheorie der Ionenkristalle, *Z. Phys.* **75** (1932), 1-18.
- 14 **Fumi F.G. and Tosi M.P.**, Ionic sizes and Born repulsive parameters in the NaCl-type alkali 361 halides-I, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids* **25** (1964), 31-43.; **Tosi M.P. and Fumi F.G.**, Ionic sizes and Born repulsive parameters in the NaCl-type alkali 359 halides-II, *J. Phys. Chem. Solids* **25** (1964), 45-52.

- 15 **Leibfried G.** and **Haln H.**, Zur Temperaturabhängigkeit der Elastischen Konstantaen von Alkalihalogenidkristallen, *Z. Phys.* **150** (1958), 497-525.
- 16 **Mori S.** and **Hiki Y.**, Calculation of the third- and fourth-order elastic constants of alkali halide crystals, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.* **45** (1978), 1449-1456.
- 17 **Bhalla V., Singh D.** and **Jain S.K.**, Mechanical and thermophysical properties of cerium monpnictides, *Int. J. Thermophys.* **37** (2016), 33 (17 pp.).
- 18 **Langueur H.** and **Kassali K.**, Density functional study of the carbon dependence of the structural, mechanic, thermodynamic, and dynamic properties of SiC alloys, *Int. J. Thermophys.* **38** (2017), 41.
- 19 **Singh D., Kaushik S., Pandey S. K., Mishra G.** and **Bhalla V.**, Mechanical and thermophysical properties of neptunium monpnictides, *VNU J. Sc. Math- Phys.* **32** (2016), 43-53.
- 20 **Bhalla V., Singh D., Mishra G.** and **Wan M.**, Mechanical and thermophysical properties of neptunium monpnictides, *J. Pure Appl. Ultrason.* **38** (2016) 23-27.
- 21 **Singh D., Kaushik S., Tripathi S., Bhalla V.** and **Gupta A.K.**, Temperature dependent elastic and ultrasonic properties of berkelium monpnictides, *Arab. J. Sci. Eng.* **39** (2014), 485-494.
- 22 **Mason W.P.** and **Batemann T.B.**, Relation between third order elastic moduli and the thermal attenuation of ultrasonic waves in nonconducting and metallic crystals, *J. Acoust. Soc. Am.* **40**, (1966), 852.
- 23 **Yadav R.R.** and **Singh D.**, Ultrasonic attenuation in lanthanum monochalcogenides, *J. Phys. Soc. Jpn.* **70** (2001) 1825-1832.
- 24 **Singh D., Pandey D. K., Singh D.K.** and **Yadav R.R.**, Propagation of ultrasonic waves in neptunium monochalcogenides, *Appl. Acoust.* **72** (2011), 737-741.
- 25 **Bhalla V., Singh D., Mishra G.** and **Wan M.**, Mechanical and thermophysical properties of europium monochalcogenides, *J. Pure Appl. Ultrason.* **38** (2016), 23-27.
- 26 **Cousin C.S.G.**, New relations between elastic constants of different orders under central force interactions, *J. Phys. C: Solid State Phys.* **4** (1971), 1117-1123.
- 27 **Hiki Y.** and **Granato A.V.**, Anharmonicity in noble metals; higher order elastic constants, *Phys. Rev.* **144** (1966), 411-419.
- 28 **Bhalla V., Kumar R., Tripathy C.** and **Singh D.**, Mechanical and thermal properties of praseodymium monpnictides: an ultrasonic study, *Int. J. Mod. Phys. B* **27** (2013), 1350116 (28 pp.).
- 29 **Karki B.B., Ackland G.J.** and **Crain**, Elastic instabilities in crystals from ab-initio stress-strain relations. *J. Phys.: Condens. Matter* **9** (1997), 8579-8590.
- 30 **Kaushik S., Bhalla V.** and **Singh D.**, Temperature dependent elastic and ultrasonic properties of silver halide crystals, *J. Pure Appl. Ultrason.* **36** (2014), 85-90.
- 31 **Kumar A., Singh D., Thakur R.K.** and **Kumar R.**, Mechanical and thermophysical properties of lutetium monochalcogenides: an ultrasonic study, *J. Pure Appl. Ultrasonic.* **39** (2007), 43-48.
- 32 **Kor S.K., Singh D.** and **Srivastava A.K.**, Ultrasonic studies of thulium monochalcogenides, *Indian J. Pure Appl. Phys.* **43** (2005), 355-358.